

Integration for resource efficiency and circular operations

A northern wood company has developed an integrate in which three business lines make the most out of resources by adaption of circular operative models. Woodchips are grinded into chemi-thermomechanical pulp, which is used as a raw material for the middle layer of paper-board. In the pulp mill, sawdust is cooked into cellulose pulp, which is then used without bleaching as a raw material for saturating base kraft papers. Furthermore, old corrugated containers are processed into fibres, which are used as a raw material in the production of the saturating base kraft papers. The black liquor created as a by-product of cellulose pulp production is utilised in the energy production of the mill. Lastly, nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorus, generated as a side stream in production are recovered for use in farmland.

Image: KotkaMills

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Wood pulp is used with high resource efficiency as sawdust is cooked into wood pulp.
- ▶ The level of recycling of the saw dust used pulp and the corrugated containers for the saturating kraft papers as well as nutrient recycling shows optimized waste management operations.
- ▶ Since black liquor that is generated by the production is used to power the plant, the business model also presents high energy efficiency.
- ▶ The business model of the three plants that is based on industrial symbiosis and exchange of wooden waste to create materials and energy is innovative.

Regional coverage and transferability

Especially in the wood intensive Northern European countries, integrated way of operations have potential for creating energy and material efficiency, as well as recirculation of materials for reuse. However, realization of such efficient production ecosystems require new partnerships and high commitment. Furthermore, establishment of circular integrates require favourable regulation that often take years to achieve.

